

THE ROLE OF COMPETENCY GAP ANALYSIS IN ENHANCING WORKFORCE PERFORMANCE AND PRODUCTIVITY WITH REFERENCE TO HERITAGE FOODS INDIA LIMITED

¹ V. Divya, ² S Susmitha

¹Assistant Professor, ²MBA Student

DEPARTMENT OF MBA

Sree Chaitanya College of Engineering, Karimnagar

ABSTRACT

A lot of things having to do with e-Learning and Human Resource (HR) revolve on competencies. When defining what it takes to do a job well, human resources departments often turn to competency descriptions. Both candidates and workers may acquire these skills via formal education and work experience. In order to locate qualified individuals, human resources departments often have to compare applicants' necessary and attained competencies. The same thing happens with online education. The competencies that will be gained upon successful completion of a program or course of study should be detailed in the program's or program's requirements. The goal of this study is to provide a framework for (semi-)automatic competence matching by analyzing current methods to competence modeling and expanding upon their limitations.

A crucial problem in BPM is the assignment of tasks to agents, whether they be human or automated, for the purpose of performing or supervising those tasks. Work assignment rules are often created using role-based techniques. A role is a combination of competencies and privileges needed to do a task. This paper's goal is to provide a competency-based solution to the activity assignment dilemma. To prepare for domain-specific user development through competency-based training, it is necessary to conduct a competency gap analysis, which can be aided by an ontology-based competency model. This model

also helps in identifying the competencies that already exist in an organization as well as those that are required by workflow activities.

In the global competition, the firm's performance is heavily dependent on the expertise and knowledge of its people. One of the most important things that helped get the system off the ground was an acceptance strategy that included things like a motivated group of pilots, the workers' council, management's backing, and plenty of information and clarity on the system's goals and purpose. Having a solid working relationship with the workers' council is crucial. Last but not least, the project needs sufficient organizational and human resources.

I. INTRODUCTION

Competency Gap is the difference between the current competency level (CCL) of your employees and the required competency level (RCL).

In other words, the disparity or difference between the existing abilities and skills of your employees and what are expected of them in achieving the objectives that you want them to achieve are the skill and knowledge gap.

"Competency" consists of the skills and knowledge required by employees to effectively perform their jobs or specific tasks that you assign to them from time to time.

a) To bridge the gap between employee specifications and job and organizational requirements:

An employee's present specifications may not exactly meet the organization requirements irrespective of his past experience, knowledge, skills, qualifications etc. for this reason the management identifies the differences or gaps between employee specifications and job and organizational requirements. Training is required to bridge these gaps by developing and molding the employee skills and abilities in tune with organizational requirements.

b) Organizational viability and the Change process:

In order to survive and grow, the organization must continuously adopt to the changing environment. For this purpose, it should upgrade its capabilities by conducting training programmes which foster the initiative and creativity of employees and help them to prevent the obsolescence of skills.

C) Changing technology:

As technology is changing very fast, an organization in order to be effective should adopt the latest technologies like mechanization, Computerization and automation. Increasing use of latest technologies and techniques require good training for this purpose the organization should train the employees to enrich them in the areas of changing technical skills and knowledge.

d) Internal mobility:

Training also become necessary when there is internal mobility i.e. , when an employee is promoted or when there is some new job or occupation to performed due to transfer. When an employee is chosen for higher level jobs,

he/she should be trained before assigning the responsibilities.

e) Sound human relations:

As the approach to HRM has shifted from commodity approach to the partnership approach beyond human relations approach, management has to maintain sound human relations in addition to maintaining harmonious industrial relations,. So, training in human relations is necessary to deal with problems like transfer, interpersonal and inter group conflicts and maintain sound human relation.

NEED OF STUDY:

The purpose of study is to learn the practical applicability of the theoretical knowledge gained about Competency Gap process.

- To gain knowledge about, the process of training and development in Heritage
- To know the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the process of Competency Gap in training and development in Heritage.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

This study covers all aspects of Competency Gap in training and development programs in HERITAGE. This study covers the New Entrant Manager response towards the training programs in the organization.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To analyze and examine the effectiveness of Competency Gap Analysis programmes in HERITAGE.
2. To assess how often training programmes are conducted and how much are the employees satisfied.

3. To study to what extent the training programmers are applicable to their jobs.
4. To study the employee's opinion on the training and development in HERITAGE.

III. METHODOLOGY

The basic principle in the research has been adopted in the overall methodology. The following methodology has been used for meeting the requirements,

- Defining objectives
- Developing the information sources
- Collection of information
- Analysis of information
- Suggestion

The methodology followed for collection, analysis under interpretation of data in explained below.

1. RESEARCH DESIGNS

There are generally three categories of research based on the type of information required, they are

1. Exploratory research
2. Descriptive research
3. Casual research

The research category used in this project in descriptive research, which is focused on the accurate description of the variable in the problem model. Consumer profile studies, market potential studies, product usage studies, Attitude surveys, sales analysis, media research and prove ability of the information provided by the employees.

Sincere efforts were made surveys are the,

Examples of this research. Any source of information can be used in this study although most studies of this nature rely heavily on secondary data sources and survey research.

2. Data collection method

Primary data:

It is collected through the questionnaire, a formalized instrument of asking information directly from respondent demographic characteristics, attitude, belief and feelings through personal contacts. Structured and on disguised form of questionnaire is used and consists of multiple choice questions.

Secondary data:

Internal secondary data about the Organization included formal data, which is generated within the organization itself, were obtained through concerned head in the organization

External secondary data generated by source the organization was used such as public available data provided by the reports of the companies. All this information is of great importance and conceptualizes and illuminates the core of the study.

3. SAMPLE DESIGN

a) Sampling unit: the study is directed towards the executive of managerial level.

b) Sample size: sample size of 100 is taken in this study

4) DATA ANALYSIS

Simple analysis method is followed for analyzing the data pertaining to different

dimensions of employees. Simple statistical data like percentage are used in the interpretation of data pertaining to the study. The results are illustrated by means of bar charts.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- Due to constraint of time and resources, the study was conducted in the regional sector as Heritage and the results of the study cannot be generated.
- The accuracy of the analysis and conclusion drawn entirely depends upon the reliability to cover maximum departments of the employees, but the study may not fully reflect the entire opinion of the employees.
- In the fast moving/changing employees behavior, new and better things may emerge in the near future, which cannot be safeguarded in this report.

IV. DETERMINATION OF COMPETENCY GAP

Determining the skills and knowledge gaps of employees is a necessary part of your human resource plan.

In order to identify the competency gap of any employee, it is necessary to determine the following:

- The types of competencies required to perform the job well,
- The required competency level required of the employee
- Industry competency standard for each of the positions in the organization

The majority of competencies relate to functional and behavioral competencies of employees and vary from the top level to the lowest. Core competencies are common competencies for every position in the organization.

The required competency level is the standard of performance for each duty based on industry standard. The "industry" refers to the type of industry in which your organization is carrying out its activities.

The standard can range from 3 as being satisfactory to 4 as having performed beyond the expectation of the organization or 5 as having performed to industry standard. An employee who has attained a rating of "5" is considered as an expert in his or her field.

You need to carefully examine anything lower than this.

The employee's competency is assessed at the end of a certain period of time, usually one year and no shorter than nine months.

Normally the current competency level is based on ratings such as:

- 1 for beginner's level
- 2 for below standard
- 3 for satisfactory performance
- 4 for performance beyond expectation, and
- 5 for performance to industry standard

For example, if the RCL is 4 and the assessment by the supervisor indicates that the employee's CCL is 3, the "competency gap" is "1" expressed as a percentage.

If the CCL is 4 and the RCL is 3, the employee had exceeded expectation.

Use of Technology in Determining Employee Competency

HRD software is usually employed to manage employee competencies due to its complexity.

The determination of competency gap is a part of this.

The HRD system is also used to:

1. to find the best "fit" between the employee's competencies to the requirements of his or her current position and whether with the current competencies, the employee can perform other types of job and to what degree
2. to manage employees' application for training based on the needs of their current jobs
3. to keep and maintain records of expenses on training / courses attended by each employee
4. to determine whether a new employee is ready for confirmation in service, and
5. to help executives in performing training needs analysis while in the process of preparing training and development programs

The Right and Responsible Use of Technology

It is necessary to use technology in determining competency gaps of employees.

Use this information in talent management, in determining the types and frequency of training that each employee is required to attend, and in employees' career development.

Technology can facilitate decision making. However, manipulation of technology is a real possibility. There are recorded instances of this happening.

In addition, the saying "garbage in, garbage out" is of real concern. Ensure accuracy of data entered into the system.

DEVELOPING A MODEL OF HR COMPETENCIES

Based on our interviews with ten HR leaders, a summary of previous research studies (Lawson, 1990; Ulrich, Brockbank, Yeung & Lake, 1995), and a frequency analysis of HR competency items used in seven companies(1), we propose a new model of HR competencies that corresponds to the emerging HR structure in many corporations. As summarized in Exhibit 2, it is a four-domain competency model which includes Core, Leadership, HR Expertise, and Consultation competencies. Depending on their roles (corporate HR leader, senior business unit generalists, HR specialists at shared service centers, HR experts at centers of expertise), different domains of HR competencies are critical for different HR professionals.

At the center of the model are the core competencies which every effective hr professional should develop. These competencies include:

Business knowledge - capacity to understand competitive issues impacting the business (e.g., market, products, technology, processes) and to understand how business can create profit and value

Customer orientation - ability in viewing issues from the perspective of customers

Effective communication - the ability to provide both verbal and written information clearly, consistently, and persuasively

Credibility and integrity - to walk what you talk, act with integrity in all business transactions, and honor personal commitments

Systemic perspective - the ability to view problems and issues in the context of the bigger

picture and understand the interrelationships among sub-components negotiation and conflict resolution skills - the capacity to reach agreements and consensus in spite of different goals and priorities

These Core competencies distinguish a highly effective HR professional from a typical one.

1. Critical competencies for senior HR generalists

For both corporate HR leaders and senior HR generalists in business units, the critical competencies lie in the domains of Leadership and Core competencies. Competencies in Consultation and HR Expertise are also desirable, but not as critical as the other two domains. Leadership competencies include:

Leadership styles - the ability to empower and trust others, to coach and develop subordinates, and to treat others with respect

Leadership skills and attributes - self-confidence, a willingness to take risks, the ability to develop and articulate vision, lead change, and sell ideas

Change advocacy - the ability to identify environmental changes that impact business and to translate them into requisite organizational changes

2. Critical competencies for HR specialists in shared service centers

For HR specialists working in shared service centers, the performance goal is to develop an efficient infrastructure that can deliver HR services consistently, responsively, and cost-effectively. Hence, HR Expertise competencies, in addition to Core competencies, are required

though the other two domains are also desirable. HR Expertise competencies include:

Knowledge - of "best-in-class" HR practices through benchmarking and environmental scanning

Ability - to design and deliver HR services effectively through process management and improvement

Ability - to apply information technology to HR

Capability - to measure the effectiveness of HR practices

3. Critical competencies for HR experts in centers of expertise

For HR experts working in centers of expertise such as those focusing on organizational change and new program design, the critical competencies are Consultation and Core. Competencies in Leadership and HR Expertise are desirable but not as critical as the other two domains.

Consultation competencies include:

Influencing skills - the ability to help others accept your viewpoints and proposals

Consulting skills - the ability to diagnose/solve problems, and contract with clients

Change facilitation and implementation skills - the ability to conceive, design, and implement programs in spite of resistance

Collaboration and team building skills - the ability to motivate team members in working toward common goals

The proposed model of HR competencies is unique in several ways. First, it differentiates the

critical competencies from desirable competencies for HR professionals in the four major roles, offering corporations a guide to a systematic and focused development of their HR professionals. Second, the importance of these competencies was found to exist, quite consistently, across a broad spectrum of industries we studied. Thus, the competencies may be considered generic and the model can be applicable to a wide range of companies. Third, the model integrates research findings from a variety of sources, including interviews reported in this study, previous survey research projects (Lawson, 1990; Ulrich, Brockbank, Yeung & Lake, 1995), and an analysis of HR competencies used in seven companies. As a result, the model's reliability and value are greater than a less expansive study would be.

How Do Corporations Acquire These New Competencies?

While quite a few research studies focus on the identification of critical competencies of HR professionals, very few studies discuss the strategies corporations can use to acquire or develop these new competencies. However, this neglected topic is critical for two reasons. First, a competency gap was observed in all the companies we studied. The HR leaders we interviewed estimated that only 10-35% of their HR professionals possess the required new competencies. Second, all HR leaders we interviewed agreed that it is much harder to develop new HR competencies than to simply identify them. Clearly, identifying the critical competencies is only the first step. Inculcating them - especially among those HR professionals who have become accustomed to the previous modus operandi - requires a significant investment of time and effort, involving the deployment of creative developmental approaches and strategies. Although recruiting HR professionals with the required new

competencies is always an option, in actual practice it has not been a major thrust or high priority for many companies for two reasons. First, because of their corporate cultures and HR philosophies, some companies may choose not to adopt a fire-and-hire strategy. Instead, they prefer to help existing HR professionals to retrain for a new set of competencies. For example, Hewlett-Packard believes that, among its own HR professionals, new opportunities for personal growth and higher business impact can serve as a catalyst to the development of new competencies. Hence, a variety of competency development programs are offered to meet the needs of existing HR professionals. Second, while some companies may take the position that the retraining of HR professionals is too costly and/or difficult and thus, the recruitment of those with the requisite competencies is a more viable alternative, these companies often encounter difficulties in recruiting HR professionals with the necessary competencies. As one would expect, the demand for HR professionals possessing the new competencies far exceeds the supply.

Because of these reasons, the HR leaders we interviewed employ a variety of strategies to ensure [TABULAR DATA FOR EXHIBIT 3 OMITTED] that the new HR competencies will be in place within three or five years. Exhibit 3 summarizes the strategies some companies are currently using. The strategies can be categorized into planning and assessment, communications, performance management, training, and development.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Is the Training program introduced new concepts in your area of working?

Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Can't say	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
No. of Employees	68	20	8	0	4	100
Percentage	68	20	8	0	4	100

INTERPRETATION:

From the above information most of the executives agree that the Training program introduced new concepts in their area of work place.

2. Is the Training program introduced new concepts in area of your personality development/Human relations?

Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Can't say	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
No. of employees	48	12	32	8	0	100
Percentage	48	12	32	8	0	100

INTERPRETATION:

From the above information most of the executives agree that the training

program introduced new concepts in area of their personality development/Human relations.

3. Is the Training program useful to you in your present job?

Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Can't say	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
No. of Employees	68	12	6	4	0	100
Percentage	68	12	6	4	0	100

INTERPRETATION:

From the above information most of the executives agree that the training program useful to them in their present job.

VI. CONCLUSION

- After participating in this training program, employers will have more knowledge to use on the job.
- The company offers orientation classes and other forms of training, such as coaching, to new employees.
- Workers may put their training to good use right away on the workplace.
- Workers are better able to take on more responsibilities at work as a result of the training program.
- For the most part, workers are putting their newly acquired knowledge to use on the job.
- Workers are expected to assume additional responsibilities inside the company in accordance with the training program.
- Workers will be more efficient thanks to the training program.

- They are now more certain in their abilities as a result of this training session.

Training had a beneficial effect on workers' actions.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

Author's Name	Title of Book
C.B. MAMORIA	PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT
SUBBA RAO	INDUSTRIAL RELATIONS AND PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT
VP MICHIEAL	HRM & HR
STEPHEN P. ROBBINS	ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR

WEBSITES:

<http://www.Heritage.co.in>

<http://www.google.com>

<http://www.citehr.com>